

MICROSCOPIC BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS DURING HEATING AND COOLING

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SUMMARY

The Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (ESEM) with a heating platform was used to observe the microscopic behaviour of composite materials during heating to 550°C and subsequent controlled cooling to room temperature. Video of these experiments captured pore formation and growth during resin decomposition as well as possible surface changes during cooling.

Keywords: ESEM, decomposition, pore formation, cooling crystallization

INTRODUCTION

Multiphysics models are being developed to predict the thermo-structural response of materials when exposed to high temperature conditions such as fires. Modelling this behaviour has largely been performed based on macroscopic response of the material. However, new models for micromechanics and heat and mass transfer require a more fundamental understanding of the microstructure being generated during the heating process and its influence on macroscopic response.

Current understanding of the microscopic response of composite materials exposed to high temperature heating is largely based images of the material taken following heating. Mouritz and Mathys [1] conducted a post-fire scanning electron microscope (SEM) examination of a GRP sample that had been degraded in the cone calorimeter while in an oxidizing (atmospheric air) environment and found delamination cracking inside of the composite. Chang [2] has found that polymer-matrix composite samples exposed to one-sided radiant heating can develop very steep temperature gradients and develop thermal gradients due to their low thermal conductivity. Chang suggests that this high temperature gradient results in delamination cracking. Morphology changes are also used in support of developing new materials with reduced flammability [3,4]. Similar to the mechanics example above, researchers typically only view the material morphology before and after the exposure leaving the cause of the change in morphology unknown.

An experimental study was performed to observe, in real-time, the changes in the microstructure of a resin sample and a composite material sample when exposed to high temperature. The microscopic changes were evaluated using an Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (ESEM) with an integrated heating stage. The material was also tested in a Thermogravimetric Analyzer (TGA) to quantify the temperatures at which the material losses mass. The observations in the ESEM were compared with the

TGA measurements to determine connections between morphology changes and mass loss.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thermogravimetric Analyzer

The thermogravimetric experiment was conducted on a Netzsch STA 449 F1 Jupiter Simultaneous Thermogravimetric Analyzer/Differential Scanning Calorimeter. The instrument is capable of controlled heating and cooling at up to 50°C/min with isothermal segments at any point and will reach temperatures up to 1500°C. In order to maximize the temperature sensitivity of the S-type sample platform thermocouples, platinum sample crucibles were used.

During the experiments reported in this paper, the instrument was raised to a temperature of 40°C at 5°C/min and held at constant temperature for 20 minutes to equilibrate prior to beginning the heating segment. During the heating segment, samples were raised to final temperatures of 610-620°C at 20°C/min. Prior to each run of the instrument, the sample chamber was taken to 92-95% vacuum, and then refilled with pure nitrogen (inert). The flow of nitrogen then maintained at a rate of 50 mL/min for the duration of the experiment. In order to maximize the quality of the data that the instrument collected, a baseline run was conducted before each sample run. The baseline run allowed for the output curves from the instrument to show only the effect of the degrading sample, thereby removing any instrument error resulting from the temperature ramp.

Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope

Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (ESEM) experiments were conducted with a FEI Quanta 600 FEG. The ESEM is equipped with a heated sample holder consisting of a heated cylindrical ceramic chamber 7.5 mm in diameter and about 5 mm deep. During experiments, a stainless steel heat shield with a 1 mm opening through which images were taken covered the top opening of the chamber. The heat shield was put in place in order to enhance temperature uniformity over the sample. The heated sample holder is capable of achieving 1000°C at heating rates up to 100°C/min. Figure 1 shows the ESEM heating platform with the heat shield removed.

Figure 1. ESEM heating platform

After loading the sample and closing the instrument, several vacuum cycles were completed to remove all oxygen from the sample chamber. The chamber was then given a low-pressure (150-400 Pascal) fill of water vapor. The water vapor was helpful in preventing charging (collection of electrons) on the sample surfaces, and the vapor pressure was varied as necessary to optimize the microscope image. Once the vacuum cycles were completed and the electron detector centered over the desired portion of the sample and initial images were taken, the sample was heated to a final temperature and then cooled. During the temperature ramps, video was recorded of the microscope output.

Approach

The TGA and ESEM were used to quantify the microscopic response of a resin sample and composite sample during heating in an inert atmosphere. In addition, the effects of cooling the material back down to room on the microstructure were also investigated. The resin sample was Derakane 411-350 vinyl ester (VE) while the composite was an E-glass/VE (Saint-Gobain 324B/Derakane 411-350) made using the VARTM process. Experiments in the TGA and ESEM were performed on resin samples at a heating rate of 20°C/min to 400°C to observe the pyrolysis process. In separate experiments, changes in the E-glass/VE composite sample microstructure were observed in the ESEM during heating at a rate of 20°C/min to 550°C and during subsequent cooling at 20°C/min back to room temperature. The composite material was also tested in the TGA at a heating rate of 20°C/min. Results from experiments in the ESEM for both materials were then compared and correlated to TGA data.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

TGA data are presented for both the pure resin and E-glass/VE samples. The results are then compared in a normalized form that shows the close TGA correlation between the two material systems. High-temperature ESEM images are then presented for each sample, and they are examined for changes that take place as the samples are heated.

Thermogravimetric Analysis Curves

Thermogravimetric analysis was performed on both an E-glass/VE sample and a resin sample. Both samples were taken from the same pieces of material as the corresponding ESEM samples. Tests were run at 20°C/min, which is the same heating rate used in the ESEM experiments. TGA data was reformulated in terms of mass fraction.

$$F = \frac{m}{m_i} \quad (1)$$

Initial sample masses are shown in Table 1. Samples were formed into thin discs, approximately 6.3 mm in diameter. At this size, they cover the entire base of the TGA sample pan, thereby yielding the maximum possible temperature sensitivity.

Table 1. TGA sample initial masses.

Sample	Initial Mass (mg)
VE 411-350 Resin	24.3
E-glass/VE 411-350	32.0

Figure 2. TGA curve of resin mass fraction remaining.

Figure 3. TGA curve of E-glass/VE mass fraction remaining.

In order to best show the close correlation between the TGA results for pure vinyl-ester resin and E-glass/VE, the data was then reformulated in terms of the mass fraction decomposed.

$$F = \frac{(m - m_f)}{(m_i - m_f)} \quad (2)$$

This fraction has a range from 1 to 0, and removes the large difference in final mass between the resin and composite samples. The difference in final mass is caused by the presence of fibers in the composite sample, which undergo minimal mass loss during heating, and as a result leave a large fraction of residual mass in the composite sample. The two TGA curves normalized by Equation 2 are plotted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. TGA curve of mass fraction decomposed for both samples.

Both materials begin to decompose gradually at 140°C. The rate of decomposition increases dramatically at about 380°C, before tapering off at 480°C. Figure 4 clearly demonstrates the resin is responsible for the mass loss in the two materials and the decomposition is similar in both cases.

Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope Images

A fully cured Derakane 411-350 resin sample was run from room temperature to 400°C at 20°C/min in the heated sample holder within the ESEM. Image field width was varied from 100-200 μm in order to examine details of the sample as it was decomposed. Figure 5a-f shows images at a series of temperatures that characterize the decomposition. The surface first appears to roughen before pores form and then grow. Once the sample exceeded 400°C and the rate of decomposition increased, the image became very unstable due to bulk motion of the sample as it degraded. As a result, no additional video was collected above this temperature.

Figure 5. ESEM images of Derakane 411-350 vinyl-ester resin.

The initial phase of decomposition in resin was observed in the microstructure to begin at about 200°C. The surface of the resin appears to become rougher as this phase begins; indicating small amounts of material are being lost from the surface, thus initiating pore formation. Figure 5b shows the resin at 251°C, with a roughened surface as described. As the temperature continues to rise above 350°C, pores begin to enlarge on the surface. Figures 5c-e show pores forming and growing to widths of 20-30 μm (typical fiber diameter is 20 μm for the composite sample).

Figure 5f shows one of the last images taken, at which point the ESEM had been set to field width of about 300 μm to show that pore formation was taking place over the whole surface, rather than just the area in which it had been focused for most of the experiment.

An E-glass/vinyl-ester sample was placed in the ESEM to observe the changes in the composite material as it was heated and cooled. Owing to the lack of gaps between fibers in the composite samples that were tested in the ESEM, it was initially difficult to find such obvious pore formation as was seen in the resin samples. This was solved through sample preparation. A sample was cut such that the fiber cross section from the woven fabric was on the surface, allowing the resin in the small gaps between the warp and weft fiber directions to be visible. In order to capture a characteristic view of the fibers, the field width was set at 370 μm , somewhat higher than in the resin experiments. The sample was then ramped to 548°C at 20°C/min. Figure 6a-f shows a progression of images of the decomposition that took place as the sample was heated.

Figure 6. ESEM images of E-glass/VE during heating.

Other than small amounts of thermal expansion, no major changes were observed below about 400°C. Due to this, images below 382°C have been omitted to save space. Unlike

the resin samples, pore formation is much less obvious in the temperature range of 300-400°C, even in the resin rich region that was focused on for the ESEM experiment used in this paper. However, the resin decomposition does appear to allow for some fiber motion over the temperature range 380-460°C. Figures 6a-c show the change in surface smoothness from 382°C to 480°C. As the sample continued to heat up, pores began to form on the surface in two locations as shown in Figure 6d; in one place along the length of a fiber that had been partially sanded off, and in another where a fiber began to drift or pull away from adjacent fibers, leaving small strings of resin in its wake. The TGA curves show that at this temperature, most of the resin is already gone, and just 7% remains. The single fiber continues to move as the temperature rises from 490°C, finally coming to rest at approximately 520°C. At this very same temperature, the surface in between fibers changes very suddenly, transitioning from the fairly smooth resin surface into a final char pore structure. Figure 7 shows a 1 mm field width view of the sample at 548°C, in which two resin-rich regions are captured. Both of these regions exhibit this large pore structure. The size and geometry of the pores depends most on the arrangement of the adjacent fibers, as they tend to conform to adjacent shapes. A typical range of pore sizes for the sample examined in this paper is 20-200 μm.

Figure 7. Large view of E-glass/VE at 548°C. Rectangle shows location of higher magnification images from heating, shown in Figures 6a-f.

The sample was then cooled at 20°C/min, back to room temperature. Figure 8a-b shows the sample at high and low temperature. While the surface appears to brighten significantly, no further structural changes are apparent.

Figure 8. E-glass/VE sample at high and low temperature after cooling.

DISCUSSION

Resin

Some interesting parallels can be drawn between the TGA data (Figure 2) and the ESEM images (Figures 5a-f) of the pure resin sample. Both sets of data confirm that there is no decomposition below 150°C, and the slow onset of decomposition is not optically apparent until about 200-250°C. It was easy to optically observe pore formation during the first stage of decomposition, characterized by the TGA data as taking place from 150-350°C. Above 350°C, pore formation was seen to accelerate, up until the point at which the image was lost at 400°C. This correlates well to the TGA data, which shows that decomposition greatly hastens at 380°C. The ESEM data confirms that pores form and continue to grow up 400°C, at which point the image was lost.

E-glass/Vinyl-ester

In contrast to the resin sample, only minor surface changes were observed in the E-glass/VE sample up to 400°C, most likely due to thermal expansion. Above this temperature, decomposition became apparent, with pores forming in the gaps between fibers and some fiber motion. The TGA curve for E-glass/VE (Figure 3) confirms that the fastest phase of decomposition is taking place from 380-460°C, which is also the temperature range where pore formation begins to become apparent in the composite. Interestingly, the composite sample clearly continued to degrade beyond 460°C, finally appearing to largely stop around 520°C.

After decomposing the sample entirely, a residual pore char structure remains in the formerly resin-rich regions that lie in gaps between the warp and weft fiber directions of the woven fiber system. This pore structure remains as the sample is cooled. While the surface appears to undergo no further changes during cooling, and DSC tests confirm that no further thermal reactions take place during cooling, the surface becomes a great

deal brighter. It becomes so much brighter, in fact, that in a few instances fibers can be seen extending down into the residual pore structure. This increase in brightness may be due to electron charging in the char formed after the resin has decomposed, or it may indicate that additional material changes are taking place. Further research is being conducted to find whether there are additional material changes during cooling.

In contrast to the result of Mouritz and Mathys [1], no cracking was observed in either sample. The lack of cracking is most likely due to the temperature uniformity and smaller scale of the samples as tested in the ESEM relative to the cone calorimeter.

CONCLUSIONS

Pure vinyl-ester resin and E-glass/VE composite samples have been investigated in a thermogravimetric analyzer, as well as in a high-temperature environmental scanning electron microscope. Pore formation was observed clearly in the resin samples from 300-400°C, prior to the loss of the image at 400°C. Pore formation was also observed in the composite samples, although it did not become obvious until 400°C. In the composite samples, the resin decomposition was observed to allow fibers to come loose from the composite entirely. Once heated to the final temperature, the composite sample exhibited a residual pore structure, primarily in the resin-rich regions between warp and weft fiber directions. The size of the pores in this structure depended most largely on the adjacent arrangement of the fibers, and a range of sizes for the sample used in this paper was found to be 20-200 µm. During cooling, the surface of the composite sample appeared to become highlighted. No cracking was observed in either sample. The lack of cracking is most likely due to the temperature uniformity.

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